

KWARA STATE UNIVERSITY, MALETE

The Green university For Community Development and Entrepreneurship

Faculty of Management and Social Sciences

**IMPACT OF SALES PROMOTION ON BUSINESS PERFORMANCE
(A STUDY of KAMWIRE MANUFACTURING COMPANY, KWARA
STATE)**

BY

OLAWALE ABRAHAM IBRAHIM

21/27BA/01412

JUNE, 2025

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**BEING A RESEARCH PROJECT SUBMITTED TO DEPARTMENT OF
BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT
OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF BACHELOR OF
SCIENCE (B.Sc) DEGREE IN BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION IN THE
DEPARTMENT OF BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP, FACULTY
OF MANAGEMENT AND SOCIAL SCIENCES, KWARA STATE
UNIVERSITY MALETE, NIGERIA**

JUNE, 2025

DECLARATION

I, **Olawale Abraham Ibrahim**, hereby declare that this research project titled “**Impact of Sales Promotion on Business Performance: A Study of Kamwire Manufacturing Company, Kwara State.**” is a result of my original academic work carried out under the supervision of **Dr. Ismaila Yusuf**.

The ideas, analyses, and findings presented in this study are my own, except where specific references have been made to the work of other researchers, which have been duly acknowledged. This project has not been submitted previously, in whole or in part, for the award of any degree or diploma in any other institution.

Olawale Abraham Ibrahim

Researcher

Signature and Date

CERTIFICATION

I hereby certify that **Olawale Abraham Ibrahim**, with Matric Number **21/27BA/01412**, carried out this research work titled **Impact of Sales Promotion on Business Performance: A Study of Kamwire Manufacturing Company, Kwara State.** under my supervision and that this research work has been read and approved as meeting the requirements of the Department of Business and Entrepreneurship, Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Kwara State University, Malete, for the award of Bachelor of Science (B.Sc.) Degree in Business Administration.

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DEDICATION

This research work is first and foremost dedicated to the Almighty God.

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ABSTRACT

Sales promotion plays a vital role in strengthening business performance, especially in highly competitive and economically challenging environments. In Nigeria, manufacturing companies face persistent challenges such as fluctuating consumer purchasing power, market saturation, and intense competition. These challenges are compounded by insufficiently strategic promotional practices, resulting in sales campaigns that often fail to align with consumer expectations or seasonal demands. The aim of this study is therefore to examine the relationship between sales promotion and business performance, focusing on Kamwire Manufacturing Company in Kwara State. Specifically, the research objectives include assessing the effects of consumer promotion on purchase decisions, evaluating the impact of promotional value on brand recognition, and analyzing the influence of target audience and seasonal timing on inventory turnover and operational efficiency. The study adopted a survey design, employing a structured questionnaire distributed to 171 randomly sampled employees of Kamwire Manufacturing Company. Data were analyzed using simple percentages and regression analysis with SPSS version 20. Findings revealed that sales promotion has a significant positive influence on key business performance indicators, including consumer purchasing behavior, brand visibility, inventory turnover, and operational efficiency. However, the results also indicated that poorly timed or misaligned promotions could limit these benefits. The study concludes that strategically designed sales promotions, aligned with consumer preferences and seasonal opportunities, can greatly improve business outcomes. It is recommended that Kamwire Manufacturing Company adopt data-driven and consumer-focused sales promotion strategies, invest in proper documentation and evaluation of promotional expenditures, and leverage seasonal timing to maximize promotional impact and long-term competitiveness.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

In today's highly interconnected global economy, sales promotion has emerged as a fundamental element of contemporary business strategies, enabling organizations to adapt to changing market conditions, intense competition, and evolving consumer preferences. Businesses worldwide face numerous challenges, including rapid technological advancements, heightened consumer expectations, and fluctuating economic landscapes. Consequently, sales promotion has become an essential mechanism for driving immediate sales, cultivating customer loyalty, and improving brand visibility. Companies increasingly depend on sales promotions not only to enhance revenue during specific timeframe but also to align with their overarching marketing goals. Sales promotion constitutes a vital aspect of the marketing mix, working in tandem with advertising, public relations, and personal selling. Its primary aim is to deliver value to consumers and stimulate prompt purchasing decisions, often through incentives such as discounts, rebates, contests, and loyalty programs. In an age where consumers possess greater knowledge and are more selective than ever, businesses must adopt innovative promotional tactics to stand out in the marketplace. The effectiveness of communicating a product's value proposition through promotional efforts is often a key factor in a business's ability to retain market share and attract new customers. The global business landscape has become exceedingly competitive, with firms competing for attention not only in their local markets but also on an international scale. This intensified competition has resulted in increased promotional spending as organizations endeavor to sustain visibility and relevance. Economic uncertainties, including inflation, disruptions in supply chains, and variable consumer demand, have highlighted the critical role of sales promotions in maintaining business performance. Companies across the globe are utilizing promotional

strategies to navigate these challenges by encouraging product trials, increasing usage rates, and enhancing brand loyalty within a competitive environment.

In Africa, the landscape of sales promotion illustrates both the potential and obstacles of operating within a diverse and rapidly evolving market. The continent is marked by a burgeoning middle class, heightened urbanization, and swift adoption of digital technologies. These elements have reshaped the interaction between businesses and consumers, paving the way for innovative promotional approaches. Nevertheless, Africa continues to grapple with enduring issues such as income disparity, inadequate infrastructure, and political instability, which can hinder the effectiveness of conventional promotional methods. In this context, sales promotions often act as a mechanism to bridge affordability gaps and cultivate consumer trust in a region where purchasing power is typically constrained. Companies implement strategies such as bundled offers, price reductions, and giveaways to appeal to price-sensitive consumers while fostering long-term loyalty. Sales promotions extend beyond mere tactical instruments; they are essential for achieving strategic goals, including market share expansion and entry into new markets. The rising competition from international brands entering African markets has further motivated local enterprises to adopt more advanced and consumer-focused promotional strategies.

Focusing on Nigeria, the largest economy in Africa, the importance of sales promotion becomes increasingly clear. The business environment in Nigeria is characterized by fierce competition, economic instability, and evolving consumer preferences. Over the years, companies in Nigeria have encountered considerable obstacles due to inflation, currency depreciation, and a decrease in consumer purchasing power. These economic conditions have made it imperative for businesses to adopt innovative promotional strategies to boost sales and sustain profitability. Numerous Nigerian enterprises have resorted to sales promotions as a means to mitigate the negative impacts of economic downturns, ensuring their products

remain competitive in the market. Sales promotion holds particular significance in industries such as manufacturing, retail, and telecommunicating, where competition is intense and consumer loyalty is challenging to achieve. Promotional initiatives, including discounts, seasonal offers, trade incentives, and loyalty programs, have become vital instruments for engaging consumers and driving sales. Businesses frequently synchronize their marketing strategies with significant holidays or cultural events to enhance their effectiveness. Sales promotions not only drive immediate sales but also improve customer perceptions of a brand's worth, thereby fostering long-term success for the business. In Nigeria, despite the prevalent use of sales promotions, numerous businesses encounter difficulties in the effective execution and management of these activities. A disconnect between promotional tools and consumer preferences can result in wasted resources and reduced returns on investment. Furthermore, the absence of adequate documentation and assessment of promotional spending can prevent businesses from grasping the actual impact of their initiatives. These issues underscore the necessity for companies to embrace a more strategic approach to sales promotion, utilizing consumer insights and market trends to enhance their results.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

One of the most significant challenges confronting businesses in Nigeria is the difficulty in effectively aligning sales promotion strategies with the distinct needs and preferences of their target markets. Although sales promotion is an essential element of the marketing mix, it frequently falls short of achieving its goals due to inadequate strategic planning, poor timing, and a limited understanding of market dynamics. This misalignment often leads to ineffective campaigns that fail to generate substantial consumer engagement, resulting in stagnant sales and a decline in market share. This issue is particularly acute in the manufacturing sector. Companies such as Kam-Wire Manufacturing Company operate in fiercely competitive landscapes where consumer purchasing power is constrained and price sensitivity is

pronounced. Despite efforts to implement promotional activities like discounts, rebates, and seasonal offers, many businesses find it challenging to convert these initiatives into measurable results, such as increased sales, greater brand visibility, or enhanced operational efficiency. The inability to optimize sales promotion strategies not only affects short-term sales performance but also jeopardizes long-term business viability.

A critical factor contributing to this challenge is timing. Numerous promotional campaigns are launched without adequately considering essential elements such as seasonal demand fluctuations, consumer behavior trends, and competitive actions. For Instance, launching a sales promotion during a period of low demand or failing to leverage peak seasons can render the campaign ineffective, resulting in wasted resources. This problem is further escalated by the absence of data-driven tactics to monitor, analyze, and refine promotional efforts, preventing businesses from learning from previous initiatives or adapting to evolving market conditions. Furthermore, inadequate financial oversight and insufficient documentation of promotional expenditures significantly worsen the situation. Numerous businesses lack a comprehensive understanding of the cost-benefit analysis associated with their sales promotions. This absence of clarity complicates the evaluation of the genuine effects of promotional efforts on overall business performance, leading to misallocated resources and lost opportunities for optimizing returns. In a market such as Nigeria, where consumers are becoming increasingly knowledgeable and selective, these challenges are aggravated. Consumers often expect more than mere price cuts; they prioritize value, trust, and quality in their buying choices. Companies that do not provide these essential elements through strategically designed promotional initiatives risk diminishing their competitive advantage, especially in sectors where substitutes and alternatives are easily accessible. Consequently, the primary question this research aims to explore is: How can sales promotion strategies be effectively crafted and executed to align with consumer preferences, enhance

timing and targeting, and yield measurable improvements in business performance? This study will concentrate on examining the specific ways in which sales promotion affects key performance indicators, such as consumer purchasing behavior, inventory turnover, and brand visibility, utilizing Kam-Wire Manufacturing Company in Ilorin as a case study.

1.3 Research Questions

This research attempts to assess the relationship between sales promotion and business performance. The research questions are centered around the following question:

- i. To what extent does consumer promotion affect consumer purchase in Kam-Wire manufacturing company?
- ii. To what extent does promotional value have a significant impact on brand recognition in Kam-Wire manufacturing company?
- iii. To what extent does the target audience have a significant effect on inventory turnover in Kam-Wire manufacturing company?
- iv. How does seasonal timing impact operational efficiency in Kam-Wire manufacturing company?

1.4 Research Objectives

The primary objective of this research is to examine the impact of sales promotion on business performance. The specific objectives of this study include:

- i. To determine the extent to which the consumer promotion affects consumer purchasing behavior in Kam-Wire manufacturing company.
- ii. To assess the significant impact of promotional value on brand recognition in Kam-Wire manufacturing company.
- iii. To analyze the effect of the target audience on inventory turnover in Kam-Wire manufacturing company.
- iv. To evaluate how seasonal timing impacts operational efficiency in Kam-Wire manufacturing company.

1.5 Research Hypothesis

In accordance with the above research objectives, this study was guided by the following null hypothesis.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between consumer promotion and consumer purchasing behavior in Kam-Wire manufacturing company.

H₀₂: There is no significant impact of promotional value on brand recognition in Kam-Wire manufacturing company.

H₀₃: Target audience has no effect on inventory turnover in Kam-Wire manufacturing company.

H₀₄: There is no significant difference between seasonal timing and operational efficiency in Kam-Wire manufacturing company.

1.6 Significance of the study

Sales promotion undeniably plays a significant role in the success of business organizations. This study aims to thoroughly assess the extent of sales promotion's impact on the performance of these organizations. Given the crucial function of sales promotion, the findings of this research are expected to contribute positively to enhancing business performance, particularly in terms of sales volume and profitability. This project will serve as a valuable resource for future researchers interested in exploring this specific topic. Additionally, it will provide insights for individuals aspiring to establish their own businesses, guiding them on how to operate effectively.

1.7 Scope of the study

This research work will concentrate on sales promotion and business performance, using Kam-Wire Manufacturing as a case study. This research covers the period from 2019 to 2024 of Kam-Wire Manufacturing, this case study will be used based on easy and accessible means of information.

1.8 Operationalization

The operationalization of my topic (Impact of Sales promotion on Business Performance) is as follows:

- Division of my topic into two constructs
- Division of constructs into two variables

Division of my topic into two constructs

The two constructs in my topic are:

- Sales Promotion
- Business Performance

Where;

$$Y = f(X)$$

Y= Sales Promotion (Independent Variables)

X= Business Performance (Dependent Variables)

$$Y = f(y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4, \dots, i)$$

$$X = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, \dots, ii)$$

Hence: $Y_i = f(X_n)$, $i = Y_{ii}, Y_{iii}, Y_{iv}$, $n = X_{ii}, X_{iii}, X_{iv}$

Y_i = Consumer Promotion

X_i = Consumer Purchase

Y_{ii} = Promotional Value

X_{ii} = Brand Recognition

Y_{iii} = Target Audience

X_{iii} = Inventory Turnover

Y_{iv} = Seasonal Timing

X_{iv} = Operational Efficiency

1.9 Operational Definition of Terms

Sales Promotion: Sales promotion can be defined as a short-term marketing strategies or activities aimed at stimulating immediate consumer purchasing, increasing sales, or enhancing the demand for a product or service.

Business Performance: Business performance can be defined as the extent to which a business meets its goals and objectives through the assessment of various key metrics, including profitability, operational efficiency, sales growth, market share, and levels of customer satisfaction.

Brand Recognition: Brand recognition refers to the extent to which consumers can identify and recall a brand due to promotional efforts aimed at increasing visibility and awareness.

Consumer Promotion: Consumer promotion is the term used to describe promotional activities and incentives created especially to entice consumers to take quick action, which involves buying a product, trying it out, or becoming more involved with the company.

Consumer Purchase: This is the decision-making process by which a consumer buy a product or service to fulfill a need or desire.

Inventory Turnover: Inventory turnover can be defined as the rate at which products are sold and replenished during promotions, indicating how well promotions stock are managed and how demand is met.

Operational Efficiency: This refers to how well a business manages expenses in relation to output during promotional periods, taking into account the potential effects of promotions on output and service delivery.

Promotional Value: Promotional Value refers to the actual or perceived benefits that a promotion provides to the customer, such as a percentage reduction in price, complimentary shipping, or a free item included with a purchase.

Seasonal Timing: Seasonal timing refers to the strategic planning and execution of marketing activities or promotions based on specific seasons, holidays, or times of the year.

Target Audience: Target audience is a specific group of customers the promotional campaign is directed towards, which may include new customers, existing customers, or a specific demographic group.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Preamble

This chapter examined the literature derived from various studies that contributed to the understanding of sales promotion and business performance. Additionally, it includes a conceptual review, a theoretical review, an empirical review, and identifies gaps in the existing literature. At the end of this review, the reader is expected to gain a fundamental understanding of the relationship between sales promotion and business performance.

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 The Concept of Sales Promotion

Sales encompasses all actions undertaken by a business to market and sell its products and services. More broadly, a sale can be characterized as a mutual agreement in the financial market, wherein a buyer and seller establish a specific price for a security. The essence of sales lies in the capacity to motivate others to act and make choices that culminate in a purchase (Tracy, 2007). Additionally, it is described as the personal exchange of information aimed at altruistically convincing a potential customer to acquire a product that meets their individual needs (Thomas and Raymond, 2004).

The influence of sales promotion on sales and customer loyalty has been well-documented in marketing and sales management literature. Hardie (1991) describes sales promotion as a temporary value incentive designed to generate interest in purchasing a product or service. This incentive is directed towards both intermediaries and consumers, often taking the form of coupons, rebates, samples, and sweepstakes. Kotler (2003) characterizes sales promotion as an essential component of marketing strategies, comprising a variety of short-term incentive tools aimed at encouraging quicker or larger purchases of specific products or services by consumers. While advertising provides a reason for purchasing, sales promotion

delivers a compelling incentive (Booner & David, 2017). According to Palmer (2004), sales promotion uniquely offers an additional motivation for consumer action. It serves as a method for firms to engage with their target market. Similarly, Nwankwo (1996) notes that sales promotion encompasses marketing activities beyond personal selling, advertising, and publicity, which enhance consumer purchasing and dealer effectiveness, including displays, shows, demonstrations, and various non-routine selling efforts. Blanchard et al., (1999) further assert that sales promotion consists of a range of short-term promotional strategies employed by marketers to encourage immediate purchases. Jefkins (1985) adds that sales promotion includes special promotional initiatives, as a rule of limited duration, at the point of sale or purchase. He also points out that such promotions can foster the development of buying habits or encourage bulk purchases while potentially leading to brand switching and diminished brand loyalty. They can enhance competitiveness at the point of sale and expand consumer choices. Sales promotion encompasses various activities aimed at generating interest, encouraging trial, or facilitating purchases by end customers or other participants within the distribution channel (Pembi, 2017). George E. and Michael A. Blech (2013) indicates that sales promotion serves as a direct incentive, providing additional value or motivation for goods and services to the sales force, distributors, or final consumers, with the objective of driving immediate sales. Furthermore, sales promotion plays a crucial role in enhancing integrated marketing communication and building brand equity (Sherlekar, 2001). The American Marketing Association (AMA) defines sales promotion as a brand, a name, symbol, or a combination thereof, intended to identify the goods or services of a specific seller or group of sellers, thereby distinguishing them from competitors. Sales promotion is effective in increasing the volume of products purchased by existing customers (Warmke & Palmer, 2005). It is essential to attract, encourage, and persuade all potential buyers to consider a specific product. Sales promotion effectively stimulates consumer purchases at the

point of sale (Sherlekar, 2001). According to Macdonald (1988), sales promotion is fundamentally a problem-solving endeavor aimed at aligning consumer beliefs with the economic interests of the organization and its offerings. Mela, Gupta, and Lehman (2007) assert that among the various promotional strategies available, sales promotion is particularly effective in driving rapid and substantial purchases within a limited timeframe. In line with this perspective, Aderemi (2013) posits that sales promotion encompasses marketing activities that enhance the fundamental value proposition of a product (i.e., obtaining more for less) for a limited duration, thereby stimulating customer purchases and enhancing the effectiveness of the sales force. Sales promotion comprises a range of incentives and tools, primarily short-term in nature, designed to encourage quicker or larger purchases of specific products or services by consumers or trade (Mkanda, 2009).

2.1.2 Objectives of Sales Promotion

The primary aim of sales promotion is to alter the demand patterns for products and services. In essence, sales promotion encompasses three specific objectives. Firstly, it seeks to provide valuable marketing insights to potential customers. Secondly, it aims to persuade and motivate prospective buyers through effective strategies. Lastly, sales promotion serves as a powerful competitive instrument.

The specific objectives of sales promotion as outlined by Jain (2014) are:

- **Add to the stock of the dealers:** Wholesalers and retailers generally manage a diverse range of products. Their sales activities are facilitated when manufacturers reinforce their efforts through promotional strategies. When a product or service is backed by significant promotional efforts, dealers are inherently motivated to increase their inventory of those items.
- **Attract new customers:** Sales promotion strategies are crucial in drawing new customers to an organization. These new customers are individuals who are persuaded

to switch from competing firms. Tactics such as samples, gifts, and prizes are employed to motivate consumers to experiment with a new brand or to redirect their loyalty to different retailers.

- **Help the firm to remain competitive:** Many companies engage in sales promotion activities to maintain their position in a competitive market. In today's competitive landscape, no organization can avoid the obligation of implementing sales promotion strategies.
- **Increase sales in off-seasons:** Numerous products, including air coolers, fans, refrigerators, air conditioners, cold beverages, and room heaters, experience fluctuating demand based on the season. Manufacturers and retailers of these items strive to ensure a consistent demand throughout the entire year. Companies aim to stimulate the purchase of these goods even during off-peak seasons. This objective largely explains the prevalence of discounts and price reductions for such products in the market during periods of low demand.
- **Induce existing customers to buy more:** Sales promotion tools are primarily employed to encourage current customers of a company to increase their purchases. Various strategies, such as product bundling where three items are offered for the price of two and discount coupons, are among the sales promotion tools utilized by businesses to incentivize existing customers to purchase greater quantities of a particular product.
- **Introduce new products or services:** Sales promotion is frequently employed to encourage potential customers to experience new products and services. Retailers are similarly incentivized to launch these new offerings in the marketplace. Free samples are distributed by retailers during the introduction phase. Furthermore, cash or merchandise discounts may be provided to retailers to encourage them to stock new

products or engage with new services. Free samples, trade discounts, and cash discounts are fundamentally considered sales promotion strategies.

2.1.3 Types of Sales Promotion

Previous research regarding the efficacy of consumer sales promotions has predominantly concentrated on monetary incentives (Dhar and Hoch, 1996). Nevertheless, it is important to recognize that both monetary and non-monetary sales promotions are extensively utilized in practice (Tellis, 1998). There exist significant distinctions between these two categories: monetary promotions, such as price discounts, coupons, rebates, and price packs, that offer consumers immediate benefits and are characterized by their transactional nature. In contrast, non-monetary promotions, including sweepstakes, complimentary gifts, and loyalty programs, generally provide delayed rewards and are more focused on fostering relationships. Therefore, when evaluating the effectiveness of sales promotions, it is essential to consider the various forms of sales promotion available. As noted by Kotler and Armstrong (2012), Kumar and Meenakshi (2013), various sales promotion techniques are available to help organizations meet their sales promotion objectives. These techniques include the following.

2.1.3.1 Consumer Promotions

These instruments for sales promotion are designed to increase immediate customer purchasing behavior and engagement, as well as to strengthen enduring customer relationships. Consumer promotions encompass a diverse array of tools, including coupons, rebates, premiums, point-of-purchase displays, contests, sweepstakes, Price packs samples, Advertising specialties, Trade show and sponsorship.

Coupon

Coupons are certificates or vouchers that offer a discount or promotion on a product or service. It is contended that this approach can be employed to encourage customers to explore

new products, to draw customers away from rival brands, or to persuade existing customers to increase their purchases of a particular product (Ricky et al., 2005).

Point of purchase displays

In order to attract a significant number of customers to a specific product brand, numerous business organizations utilize the point of purchase (POP) technique. This sales promotion strategy involves strategically placing product displays within retail environments to motivate consumers to make purchases (Ricky et al., 2005). Furthermore, in today's technologically advanced era, this objective can also be accomplished through the internet. Retailers can establish websites that allow potential customers to regularly view new product displays. As a result of this, customers are not required to physically visit retail stores to access products that are being showcased for the first time or repeatedly.

Premium

This is a method of sales promotion in which some items are offered free or at a bargain price to customers in return for buying a specific product. This approach provides a product either at no cost or at a reduced price to encourage customer purchases. In certain cases, complimentary samples of the product are distributed to allow customers to experience it firsthand. These samples may be available at local retail locations (Ricky et al., 2005). However, it is important to recognize that the premium strategy may not yield the anticipated results, as some customers might go for a competitor's brand to take advantage of the premiums offered by that company.

Trade show and sponsorship

Trade shows represent a form of sales promotion, with various industries periodically organizing these events for their members and customers (Griffin et al., 2004). They serve to showcase products to marketing intermediaries. More importantly, trade shows are cost-effective and highly efficient, as buyers arrive with a pre-existing interest in specific

product categories. This trend underscores the growing significance of international trade shows (Ricky et al., 2004).

Rebates

Rebate is an amount paid by way of reduction or refund on what has already been paid. It is a type of sales promotion that marketers use mainly as incentives or supplements to product sales. The brand using a rebate can increase sales primarily on the promise of a discount. Which result in extra sales at their full margin (Fripp, 2015).

Exhibitions

According to Bhasin (2018), sellers aim to present their products to potential buyers, who may either be individual consumers or industrial purchasers. An exhibition commonly features a single entity displaying its goods, although it can also involve multiple participants collectively showcasing their offerings. As noted by Patten (2001), organizations may pursue various marketing objectives when participating in exhibitions, such as increasing product sales, introducing a new product line, identifying distributors or retail outlets in new markets, and seeking agents.

Bonus pack

A bonus pack refers to a uniquely packaged item that provides the buyer with an increased quantity at the standard price; for instance, it may include three bars of soap for the cost of two. Also, a bonus pack is often referred to as a special pack, it can be an additional product offered alongside another item (Solomon and Stuart 2003). Such bonus packs promote the likelihood of repeat purchases and thereby enhancing customer loyalty.

Samples

Samples are promotional offers of a limited quantity of a product. Sampling is recognized as the most effective, but most costly method to launch a new product or generate renewed interest in an existing one. While some samples are provided at no charge, others may require

a nominal fee to help cover associated expenses. Samples can be distributed through various channels, including mail, in-store giveaways, kiosks, as attachments to other products, or through advertising and email campaigns. It may be packaged together into sample packs, which can serve to promote additional products and services. Overall, sampling serves as a potent promotional strategy.

Price packs

This offers a quick, protective reaction to weaken a competitive promotion. A "price-off" refers to a reduction in the retail price of a product. This strategy is designed to encourage consumers to purchase more items and can be utilized by either the manufacturer or the retailer. To add to that, any price reduction initiated by the manufacturer is shown on the product's packaging.

Advertising specialties

These items are commonly referred to as promotional products. They are practical items that feature an advertiser's name, logo, or message and are distributed as gifts to consumers. Common instances of such items may encompass T-shirts and different forms of clothing, writing instruments, coffee cups, calendars, keychains, mouse pads, matches, tote bags, coolers, golf balls, and hats.

2.1.3.2 Trade Promotions

These promotions are aimed at intermediaries, such as retailers and wholesalers, with the objective of encouraging them to stock a particular brand and allocate shelf space for it. This strategy encompasses incentives such as buying allowances, free goods, and discounts or price off.

Buying allowance

A buying allowance refers to a temporary discount applied to the price of each unit, bale, or other product quality. According to Kotler (1997), a buying allowance is defined as the

financial compensation provided by manufacturers to retailers in exchange for their commitment to promote the manufacturers' products in specific ways. Station (1982) characterizes promotional allowances as price reductions offered by a seller as compensation for promotional activities carried out by the buyer. This practice incentivizes intermediaries to purchase items or product qualities that they might not commonly consider, particularly during the introduction of a new product.

Free goods

These are free goods or offers of additional bundle of merchandise to middlemen who buy a certain quantity. The manufacturers might offer a free item to the retailer that bears the company's name. This is an offer of a certain amount of a product to wholesalers and retailers at no cost to them but conditional on the purchase of a stated amount of the same or another product.

Discounts or price off

This refers to a direct decrease in the price of purchases made within a specified timeframe, in other words, it constitutes a discount off the list price for each case purchased during that designated period. Such discounts incentivize dealers to make bulk purchases or to introduce a new product. Dealers may utilize the discount to generate immediate profits, allocate funds for advertising, or implement price reductions for their customers.

The above discussion highlights the numerous sales promotional techniques available to businesses and organizations. Each technique offers a unique set of benefits and drawbacks. It is essential for the organization to exercise careful consideration in selecting the appropriate sales promotional strategy. All these techniques can significantly influence organizational performance, including financial outcomes, market share, and returns for shareholders (Richard et al., 2009).

2.1.4 Sales Promotion Strategies

Bush and Houston (2001) classify sales promotion strategies based on their source and intended audience as follows:

Manufacturer to Customer

Sales promotion initiatives are implemented to enhance consumer willingness to try new products. The objective is to place the product directly in the hands of consumers, with the expectation that their experience will foster a positive perception, leading to ongoing purchases and usage. Such initiatives may include free samples, discount coupons, introductory pricing, and cash rebates. Additionally, manufacturers may direct sales promotions towards consumers to bolster or increase the sales of established products. These efforts can be crucial in revitalizing a struggling brand in response to competitive pressures. The core principle of these strategies is to provide consumers with a more favorable value-to-cost ratio. Examples of these promotions include coupons included in packaging, premiums (which are low-cost gifts offered alongside a product purchase), as well as sweepstakes and contests.

Manufacturer to Retailer

Manufacturers frequently provide a direct discount on the list price for each bundle purchased within a particular period of time. This type of offer is also referred to as price-off, off-invoice, or off-list discount, which are additional bundles of merchandise for middlemen who purchase a certain quantity or who promote specific flavors or sizes.

Retailer Incentives for Inventory display

Retailers are also targeted by this initiative, which encourages them to maintain a larger inventory of products in their warehouses or stores. Also, it supports promotional efforts through advertising allowances and compensation for display allowances associated with the use of specialized displays

2.1.5 Characteristics of Sales Promotion

Effectively utilizing sales promotion requires a selective approach to leverage its strengths while mitigating its weaknesses. This strategy fosters a perception among intermediaries and consumers that they are receiving added value at no extra cost, thereby encouraging a favorable attitude towards the products. Sales promotion serves as a supplementary incentive alongside other marketing efforts. As noted by Stanly (1997), it acts as an additional motivator that encourages immediate consumer purchases. These promotional tools are designed to elicit prompt actions rather than delayed responses, and if they fail to achieve this, a noticeable increase in sales typically follows. Sales promotions are highly adaptable and can be implemented at any phase of a new product launch. They can also reinforce the selling message conveyed through personal selling efforts. Furthermore, they provide essential support to wholesalers and company sales representatives during challenging times.

The distinctive features of sales promotion include:

- Sales promotion encompasses a range of promotional activities that extend beyond traditional advertising, personal selling, and publicity efforts
- The main objective is to encourage customers to make immediate purchases, enhance dealer effectiveness, or achieve both outcomes.
- It is not mandatory, and numerous companies do not engage in this practice.
- The approach is aimed at various goals, such as sustaining sales during off-peak periods, boosting overall sales, countering competition, liquidating inventory, enhancing brand image, and introducing new products, among others.
- This strategy encompasses a diverse array of tools and incentives.
- Sales promotion initiatives involve targeted selling activities for a limited duration, characterized by short-term incentives and schemes implemented at the consumer, dealer, or salesperson levels.

- These efforts are characterized by their non-recurring nature, distinguishing them from routine activities, as they are not executed on a regular basis.
- Sales promotion incentives are easily replicable, allowing competitors to adopt similar strategies with relative ease.
- Sales promotion can be costly and may potentially impact the company's profitability negatively.
- An overreliance on sales promotions may detrimentally influence both sales figures and the company's reputation.
- It supports personal selling and advertising initiatives, serving as a bridge between the two. This synergy can enhance the overall effectiveness of other promotional strategies.

2.1.6 Advantages of Sales Promotion

Onyeka and Nebo (2000), referencing Dummermutu (1989), assert that the benefits of sales promotion stem from two fundamental characteristics: the flexibility in timing and the extensive creative options available. Sales promotions are employed for brief durations or on an occasional basis. This approach minimizes the overall costs associated with sales promotions while maintaining their effectiveness, as they are implemented at opportune moments and do not extend beyond what is required. Keegan, Moriarty, and Duncan (1995) indicated that the significant growth of sales promotion can be attributed to its unique ability to directly influence sales. During periods of economic decline, sales promotion proves to be an especially effective component of the marketing communication strategy.

2.1.7 Problems of Sales Promotion

Okpara, Anyanwu, and Inyanga (2010) indicated that contemporary sales promotions in Nigeria are frequently hindered by several issues which includes the following:

Short-terms

The length and nature of sales promotions are inherently temporary. Business firms often regard them as a temporary solution. Consumers engage with products primarily to obtain a promotional incentive. In effect, consumers are attracted to products solely during the promotional period. This trend is regrettable.

Paradox of promotion

Sales promotions are designed to enhance sales, particularly in the short term. It is paradoxical that the greater the efforts invested in boosting sales through promotional activities, the more the associated product tends to decline in popularity, resulting in decreased sales in the marketplace. This phenomenon occurs primarily because consumers often view products that are heavily promoted with distrust, as they have a genuine demand for the product itself.

Credibility problem

In Nigeria today, it is rare to find a sales promotional initiative that does not provoke complaints from consumers. There is a prevailing belief that incentives are either entirely absent or are exclusively awarded to select individuals. As a result, this situation fosters a tepid response from both consumers and the broader public towards sales promotions in Nigeria.

Sole economic appeal

Most Nigeria sales promotions stress economy. How consumers can benefit from reduced prices and more customer savings. This may be understandable, given the nation's economic straits. But these promotions may do better than simply and solely stressing economic appeals.

2.1.8 The Effectiveness of Sales Promotion

Sales promotions play a crucial role in the communication mix. In addition to being beneficial for the specific situations outlined at the beginning of this study, they significantly enhance marketing effectiveness by complementing advertising and personal selling efforts. Numerous researchers have investigated the nature of sales promotion effectiveness, exploring whether its impact is short-term or long-term, its influence on both existing and new customers, and the effects during and after the promotional period. According to Kotler (2000: 605), manufacturers can assess the effectiveness of sales promotions through three primary methods: sales data analysis, consumer surveys, and experimental approaches. Boone and Kurtz (1998: 635) observed that many consumer-oriented sales promotion techniques yield indirect responses from consumers, allowing marketers to track their effectiveness with relative ease. As with other components of the promotional mix, it is essential for marketers to evaluate the costs of promotions against their benefits. For instance, they can analyze the redemption rates of cent-off coupons, which often include printed codes to help manufacturers and retailers identify which media yield the highest redemption rates. In assessing sampling strategies, marketers aim to determine how effectively these initiatives encourage consumers to purchase the product after trying the sample. Foster (1984: 209) concluded that the primary objective of sales promotions is relatively narrow in scope. Their effects are usually short-term; for example, they can facilitate the launch of a new product, rejuvenate demand for a struggling one, or increase sales during peak periods. However, once the promotional campaign concludes, sales often decline, frequently falling below previous levels, and may require time to recover.

2.1.9 Recent Development in Sales Promotion Trends

Palmer (2022) indicates that there has been a significant rise in the utilization of sales promotions in recent years, attributed to several factors. Firstly, there is a heightened

acceptance of sales promotions among senior management, coupled with an increase in the number of qualified personnel capable of implementing these strategies. Furthermore, the current market environment applies greater pressure to achieve rapid sales results, a goal that sales promotions effectively facilitate. The market has witnessed a widespread emergence of brands, leading to intensified competitive dynamics. Due to this situation and the evolving economic landscape, consumers have become more focused on deals. This shift has created pressure on intermediaries to seek improved incentives from manufacturers and service providers. Numerous experts contend that the efficiency of advertising is diminishing as a result of rising costs and media saturation. However, advancements in targeting technology have enhanced the efficiency and effectiveness of sales promotions (Palmer, 2022). Peattie and Peattie elucidate in Jobber (2014) the factors contributing to the recent surge in sales promotions, stating that these promotions are gaining legitimacy due to their adoption by market leaders and the rising professionalism of sales promotion agencies.

The rise in impulse buying has led retailers to seek more sales promotions from manufacturers as a response to heightened consumer behavior. In certain markets, the prevalence of sales promotions compels all competitors to adopt similar strategies. The effectiveness of sales promotions can be measured more readily than that of advertising, as their impact tends to be more immediate and typically short-lived. Furthermore, the increasing expenses associated with advertising, coupled with the saturation of advertisements, diminish the overall cost efficiency of advertising efforts.

Cravens and Piercy (2006) appear to challenge this perspective, suggesting that the expenditure on sales promotions has gained significance and that the frequency of sales promotions within the telecommunications sector aligns with the views expressed by Peattie and Peattie. Over the last twenty years, the appeal of sales promotions has been on the rise. This surge in popularity can be attributed to two primary factors: the heightened demand on

management for immediate outcomes and the advent of advanced purchase tracking technologies (Peter and Donnelly, 2003).

2.1.10 Business Performance

Performance encompasses a range of both financial and non-financial metrics that provide insights into the extent to which objectives and results are achieved (Kaplan and Norton, 1992). Financial performance pertains to the quantifiable aspects of a firm's operations, expressed in monetary terms, while non-financial performance includes qualitative measures that cannot be directly quantified in financial terms, such as brand reputation, customer satisfaction, organizational effectiveness, and innovation initiatives (Nguyen et al., 2021). Financial performance is associated with a company's immediate viability, whereas non-financial performance is more aligned with long-term sustainable development (Nguyen et al., 2021). The assessment of business performance reflects the cumulative efforts directed towards fulfilling business objectives (Akal, 1992). It involves evaluating the actual outcomes of business activities in relation to their intended goals, incorporating three distinct dimensions: financial performance, product market performance, and returns to shareholders (Richard et al., 2009). Lebas and Euske (2002) provide a succinct definition of business performance, describing it as the execution of actions today that will serve as indicators for assessing significant outcomes in the future. Santo and Breto (2012) identified various dimensions of firm performance, including enhanced financial performance, profitability, and growth. This classification aligns with the perspectives presented in the research conducted by Whetten (1987) and Glick, Washburn, and Miller (2005).

2.1.10.1 Measures of Business Performance

The measurement of business performance across various critical success factors is essential for the sustainability of any organization. Performance metrics offer a cohesive set of indicators that guide managers' focus toward key strategic areas that ultimately influence

organizational performance outcomes (Dixon et al., 1990). According to Venkatraman and Ramanujam (1996), there are multiple approaches to evaluating business performance. The first approach encompasses both objective (quantitative) and subjective (qualitative) measures. The second approach distinguishes between financial metrics (such as profit and sales) and operational metrics (including quality and customer satisfaction). Lastly, the third approach differentiates between primary methods (derived from the organization itself) and secondary methods (sourced from external databases).

2.1.10.2 Financial and Nonfinancial measures of performance

As previously mentioned, performance measures are typically divided into two categories: financial and non-financial. According to Simmons (2000), financial measures are classified as objective, whereas non-financial measures are deemed subjective. He further argues that objective measures can be independently measured and proved, while subjective measures lack this capability. Financial measures are generally associated with accounting documents such as profit and loss statements and balance sheets, including items like cash reserves and provisions for bad debts. In contrast, non-financial measures do not appear in the financial statements of a company. Evaluating a firm's financial performance through financial measures is relatively straightforward, as there are established procedures and guidelines that govern these measures (Simmons, 2000). Conversely, non-financial performance measures do not adhere to the same set of rules or standards; instead, they are often linked to goal-setting, incentives, and reward systems (Otley, 2001).

The traditional management accounting literature generally endorses the utilization of financial performance measures for assessing business performance (Kaplan & Norton, 2001). Building on this foundation, Merchant (1998) and Neely (2002) argued that financial performance measures are beneficial in several critical areas: they facilitate the communication of financial objectives, provide a comprehensive overview of performance,

separate top management from operational decisions at the business unit level, offer a clear assessment of the business's status, and reduce costs associated with external financial reporting, as these measures are readily available. In a similar vein, accounting scholars have emphasized that non-financial performance measures serve as effective indicators for evaluating current or future financial performance (Ittner & Larcker, 1998; Hughes, 2000).

The increasing difference between the book value and the actual market value of firms indicates that business entities possess significant assets, such as employees, which are not reflected on their balance sheets. Johnson and Kaplan (1987) argue that financial accounting information is primarily suited for external stakeholders, raising doubts about its effectiveness for internal assessments of business performance. Hatem (2011) notes that financial metrics are inadequate and fail to comprehensively represent managerial performance. Brazel, Jones, and Zimbelman (2009) suggest that incorporating non-financial metrics can help mitigate the risk of revenue fraud. McNair, Lynch, and Cross (1990) assert that non-financial indicators are essential for operational control. Franko (2013) points out that while developing non-financial measures is beneficial and applicable in various contexts, their effectiveness in predicting the current or future state of an organization is limited; furthermore, the informational value of non-financial metrics cannot entirely substitute for financial measures. Previous researchers have argued that traditional performance metrics, which depend exclusively on financial data, are short-term, lagging indicators that inadequately address the current and future performance of firms (Tangen, 2004; Valiris & Chytas, 2005). Along with that, Eccles and Pyburn (1992) contend that financial measures can create behavioral challenges and are more focused on internal rather than external factors (Merchant, 1998). Neely (2002) emphasizes that proactive and high-performing organizations integrate both financial and non-financial measures to improve their performance. In this

context, performance metrics that combine financial and non-financial indicators are increasingly relevant in today's business landscape (Neely & Adams, 2000).

2.1.10.3 Assessment of Performance in Sales Promotion

Businesses evaluate the effectiveness of their trade sales promotion strategies to identify successful activities through various performance metrics, including product market performance, market share, and sales turnover (Richard, 2009). This evaluation encompasses the achievement of specific tasks (Robson, 2005), the attainment of optimal organizational goals (Bell, 2000), and the contribution to overall objectives (Johnson and Marshall, 2003; Dalrymple et al., 2004; Churchill and Peters, 1998; Fenwick and Amine, 1979). It specifically focuses on marketing performance (Jackson et al., 1995), return on equity, and return on investment (Jain, 1997), as well as profit, sales market share, and cash flows (Bonoma, 1998). Financial metrics, such as sales figures, are also considered (Clark, 2000; Kokinaki and Ambler, 1999). This study will primarily focus on financial measures related to sales turnover, market share, and profitability.

Sales Turnover

This is also referred to as sales volume by numerous authors, it is generally observed to rise significantly during periods when coupons or price-off promotions are available. Consumers tend to react strongly to such deals, particularly when they are effectively advertised. This metric is regarded as an indicator of marketing performance and demonstrates how swiftly sales can be generated through trade sales promotions, which often lead to temporary price reductions that can greatly enhance sales figures.

Market Share

Market share serves as a key indicator of competitiveness, reflecting a firm's performance relative to its rivals and illustrating the distribution of market size in percentage terms. This metric aids in identifying leading companies, those in the middle tier, and smaller players within the marketplace, based on their business volume or the effectiveness of business

performance management in evaluating consumer preference for a specific product in the market landscape (Nwielaghi, 2013). Nonetheless, a significant assumption associated with market share as a gauge of marketing performance is that brands with a higher market share tend to exhibit lower price elasticity.

Profitability

Profitability is essential for assessing the effectiveness of sales promotions, as it reveals whether these initiatives yield significant financial benefits for a company. Economists typically define profitability as the total revenue minus all related expenses, which encompass both explicit and implicit costs, along with the standard profit expected by management (Hofstrand, 2007). To accurately evaluate the profitability of sales promotions, researchers suggest looking at the additional revenue generated by the promotion in relation to its costs. Blattberg and Neslin (1990) contend that sales promotions should be evaluated on their capacity to produce immediate revenue boosts, while also taking into account potential long-term consequences, such as brand dilution or stockpiling behavior among loyal customers. Furthermore, when analyzing profitability, it is important to compare the profits made during the promotional period with the profits that would have been realized without the promotion (Kotler and Keller, 2016).

2.1.11 Relationship between Sales Promotion and Business Performance

The relationship between sales promotion and business performance remains a subject of debate. The extent of its influence is not clearly defined. Certain scholars argue that the effect of sales promotion on business performance is negligible and insignificant (Dekimpe and Silva-Risso, 1999; Pauwels et al., 2002; Srinivasan et al., 2000), while others contend that the impact is substantial and noteworthy (Boddewyn and Leardi, 1989; Odunlami and Ogunsiyi, 2011). Business performance in this analysis is characterized by increased sales volume and profitability. Pauwels et al. (2002), investigated the lasting effects of sales promotions on

cumulative annual sales across two product categories which includes storable and perishable goods. The results indicated that both perishable and storable product categories do not exhibit lasting impacts from sales promotions. It was found that the influence of sales promotions is temporary, usually lasting only about two weeks, and at most eight weeks for both categories. This supports the widely held belief that sales promotions yield only temporary advantages for established business. Dekimpe et al. (1999) affirm that permanent effects of sales promotions on sales volume are rare. This implies that sales promotions do not alter the long-term sales structure. They propose that the diminishing effectiveness of sales promotions may be attributed to factors such as brand selection, purchase quantity, and category-specific incidents like energy crises. Pauwels et al. (2002) argue that when consumers frequently encounter sales promotion offers, they have often already engaged with a specific brand and resulting in minimal learning from that purchase, which is easily countered by similar competitive promotions. The immediate effects of sales promotions tend to be minimal. This is primarily due to price promotions compelling consumers to make purchases and yet the influence on sales cannot solely be attributed to the accelerated purchasing behavior resulting from price reductions. Boddewyn and Leardi (1989), as referenced in Syeda et al. (2012), identify several types of sales promotions such as price reductions, free offers, premium incentives, vouchers, samples, trading stamps, charity-linked promotions, and various prize-related incentives that influence profitability by encouraging consumers to make immediate purchases. Similarly, Ailawadi and Neslin (1998), posit regarding the positive impact of sales promotions on organizational success. They concluded that consumer promotions incentivize consumers to purchase larger quantities and consume them more rapidly, leading to increased sales and, ultimately, enhanced profitability. Bamiduro (2001), Odunlami and Ogunsiji (2011), Aworemi et al. (2008), and Banabo and Koroye (2011) present a range of findings on the impact of sales promotion on profitability.

For example, Aworemi et al. (2008) concluded that price promotions negatively affected the profitability of the Niger State Transport Authority, while only advertising demonstrated a positive influence. Odunlami and Ogunsiji (2011) fundamentally opposed those of Aworemi et al. (2008), asserting that sales promotion is an effective strategy. Additionally, Bamiduro (2001) corroborated the positive correlation between sales promotion and both the consumption rate of soft drink products and the overall sales volume within the beverage industry.

2.1.12 Conceptual Framework

The framework takes a linear relationship between the independent variable on the left hand side and the dependent variable at the right hand side. The conceptual framework shows that sales promotion is a function of business performance. From the conceptual framework, business performance is measured by the level of financial performance and nonfinancial performance. In the same vein, dimensions of sales promotion include consumer promotion and trade .

Figure 2.1 Conceptual framework for sales promotion and business performance

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Push strategy of Sales Promotion

Blattberg and Neslin proposed this theory in 1993, asserting that sales can be enhanced by providing incentives to wholesalers or retailers to promote a greater volume of your product. As noted by Shimp (2003), the push theory of sales promotion strategies suggests that products are marketed to intermediaries, such as wholesalers and retailers, who then sell them to end consumers. This approach, referred to as a "push" promotional strategy, involves leveraging a company's sales personnel and trade promotion activities to enhance customer demand for a product (Koekemoer, 2004). In this model, the producer promotes the product to wholesalers, who in turn promote it to retailers, who ultimately market it to consumers. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2010), the push theory elucidates how sales promotions can influence consumers' purchasing intentions. The significance of this theory in the context of this study lies in its assertion that the chosen sales promotion strategy affects customer patronage.

2.2.2 Pull Strategy of Sales Promotion

The idea was first presented by Blaikie in 2000, focusing on the strategy of directly marketing to consumers in order to enhance the demand for a product. Kotabe (2000) asserts that the pull theory of sales promotion can be understood primarily through a customer-centric lens. In supporting this view, Aderemi (2003) describes the pull theory as a strategy that requires substantial advertising efforts to enhance awareness of a sales promotion initiative, thereby boosting consumer demand for a product. Furthermore, Kotler (2003) defines consumer sales promotion as a collection of activities designed to stimulate demand from end users or customers, who subsequently influence the product's movement through the distribution network.

2.2.3 The Combination Theory of Sales Promotion

The combination theory of sales promotion was introduced by Kotabe in 2000. This theory aims to reconcile the pull and push theories of sales promotion. Kotler (2003) concurred that the combination theory integrates both the pull and push approaches. Kotler (2012) posited that the combination theory illustrates that neither the pull nor the push theory can independently enhance customer purchase intentions. Flaherty and Hunt (2007) supported this combined approach, asserting that companies should engage both retailers and consumers in their sales promotion strategies to foster collaboration that enhances customer purchasing intentions. The combination theory is valuable for examining the relationship between consumer sales promotion and consumer patronage. Marketers have the option to integrate both push and pull strategies in their sales promotion efforts, depending on the specific challenges they encounter in their respective markets. They examine and evaluate the fluctuations within the marketplace to identify the sales promotion strategy that will be implemented at a specific time. The push and pull techniques are referred to as appropriation and generation systems, which depend on a combination of forecasts and specific customer needs (Hinkelman and Sibylla, 2005). In push marketing strategy, companies or designated agents focus on delivering substantial quantities of products to their clientele. To encourage wholesalers and intermediaries to advocate for and distribute these products with various incentives provided. These incentives may include discounts for wholesalers, credit terms for stock acquisition, as well as bonuses and rebates. This approach involves manufacturers promoting their products to wholesalers, who subsequently market them to retailers, who in turn sell to the final consumers (Douglas and Graig 2012). Conversely, the pull strategy prioritizes the generation of market demand for the product, directing all promotional efforts towards the end users. Once demand is established, customers purchase the product from retailers, who acquire it from wholesalers, who ultimately source it from the manufacturers.

Incentives in the pull strategy are aimed at the end users and may include giveaways, prize contests, and coupons (Cornish, 2013).

This project will explore the combination theory of sales promotion, which merges both push and pull strategies. The aim of this theory is to boost product demand within the distribution channel by pushing products to wholesalers, who then promote them to their network of retailers. These retailers showcase the products in their stores for consumers to see and purchase. Furthermore, this theory highlights the significance of the pull strategy, arguing that effective marketing communication should leverage advertising media to create awareness and desire, ultimately drawing consumers into the store to make their purchases.

2.3 Empirical Review

Fernandes and Dias (2024) examined the impact of digital sales promotions on e-commerce platforms. Their findings indicated that strategies such as flash sales, time-sensitive offers, and complimentary shipping significantly influence online consumer behavior. Nonetheless, the success of these promotional tactics is largely contingent upon the design of user experience (UX) and the personalization of the offers. The statistical analysis indicates that consumers tend to respond more favorably when promotions align with their browsing history or individual preferences.

Teixeira and Kallas (2024) looked into how customer buying habits changed overtime and how promotional tactics affected those changes. Their findings indicate that price reductions, limited-time offers, and "buy one, get one free" promotions significantly influence consumer choices in both physical and online retail environments. Additionally, they noted that cultural and social factors play a substantial role in shaping consumer responses to these promotional tactics.

The study of (Ayenew, 2023) noted a systematic review that underscored the significance of sales promotion in enhancing organizational performance. The research emphasized the

necessity of aligning promotional strategies with other components such as advertising and direct marketing to achieve best outcomes. The study also made a point that excessive reliance on promotions without strategic framework may undermine brand value.

(Banerjee and Ghosh, 2023) conducted an analysis on the impact of social media promotions on online sales. The report showed that promotions featuring time-sensitive offers and those driven by influencers, particularly through platforms like Instagram and TikTok, greatly enhance consumer engagement and sales figures. The research underscored the necessity of effectively targeting the appropriate audience via digital channels to achieve optimal results.

According to Kim et al. (2023), promotions that offer discounts and loyalty benefits are essential for promoting recurring business, especially in industries like retail and consumer products. The study revealed that while temporary discounts may lead to immediate increase in sales, it is loyalty programs that significantly improve continuous consumer engagement and support long-term revenue growth.

Saha and De (2022) in their research investigated the relationship between the intensity of promotions and the variability of sales volume in competitive markets. Their research indicated that while aggressive promotional efforts can lead to a temporary rise in market share, the long-term effects will depend upon the preservation of product quality and the effectiveness of pricing strategies.

(Johnson & Kumar, 2022) examined the possible negative effects associated with excessive reliance on sales promotions, highlighting the danger of eroding a brand's perceived value. Their findings implied that frequent promotional efforts can foster consumer skepticism, prompting customers to delay purchases in anticipation of discounts, ultimately jeopardizing the brand's equity in the long run.

Purwantinah (2021) noted that sales promotion is an essential component of a business success as it serves as a marketing strategy aimed at improving consumer perception of a

product by providing additional incentives, thereby motivating purchasing behavior. This research employs three indicators to assess sales promotion which are discounts, cashback offers, and voucher promotions by (Prasetio & Muchnita, 2022).

Abdeta and Zewdie (2021) conducted a thorough analysis of how promotional mix strategies affect business performance, focusing on various promotional tools like advertising, sales promotions, public relations, and personal selling to boost business outcomes. Their findings showed that companies that skillfully integrate different promotional tactics see significant improvements in customer engagement, sales, and brand visibility, ultimately resulting in higher profitability. They emphasized that the effectiveness of these strategies depends on how well they align with the specific needs of target consumers, current market conditions, and competitive dynamics.

(Jacobs et al., 2020). Suggested that organizations globally invest significant sums in sales promotions to affect consumer behavior. This perspective is supported by Palazón-Vidal and Delgado-Ballester (2019) emphasized that companies may utilize consumer sales promotions to enhance customer experiences, including enjoyment, satisfaction, and diversion, thereby shaping their attitudes toward the brand.

Weerathunga and Pathmini (2019) emphasized that impulsive buying represents an unplanned purchasing behavior characterized by randomness among consumers. The presence of sales promotional offers tends to heighten customers' desire to make purchases. The research was carried out in a supermarket setting, where factors such as price discounts, free samples, buy one get one free offer, and loyalty programs were examined as elements of sales promotion. The findings revealed a significant impact of all these variables, thereby encouraging impulse purchases. The strategic application of these techniques enhances consumer engagement and increases the number of products purchased.

(Ramadass & Antony, 2018). Examined the impact of sales promotion techniques on the purchase of durable goods, taking into account various demographic factors. The research was carried out during the festive season, a period characterized by heightened sales promotion activities from retailers and an increase in consumer purchasing frequency. The demographic factors analyzed included age, gender, monthly and total income, occupation, family structure, and the number of household members. The statistical analysis indicated that sales promotion techniques significantly affect consumer behavior, with variations in responses linked to demographic characteristics. It was noted that not all consumers engage in every stage of the buying process, as this is influenced by the information available to them and their prior experiences.

Chang (2017) opines that in the era of digitalization, no business sector remains untouched by the adoption of promotional strategies. This research specifically aimed to explore the effects of sales promotions within the tourism industry, which plays a significant role in generating national revenue. The study analyzed both price-based and non-price-based sales promotions, including membership promotions, incentives for repeat customers, buy-one-get-one-free offers, scheduled promotions, direct discounts, and gifts. The results indicate a positive correlation between sales promotions and consumer engagement, with consumers demonstrating familiarity with the promotional practices in this sector. Increased consumer involvement subsequently enhances their purchase intentions, suggesting that more effective sales promotion strategies could be developed to boost travel-related activities.

Genchev and Todorova (2017) concur that various sales promotion activities, including contests, premiums, and coupons, in relation to the purchase of durable goods, non-durable goods, and services. They posited that sales promotion serves as a crucial marketing instrument that enhances product value and encourages consumer purchases. Their findings indicated that these promotional activities significantly influence consumer buying decisions

across all product categories. Among the promotional tools, contests, lotteries, and game schemes emerged as the most impactful for services, while price reduction promotions were particularly significant for durable goods, followed by premiums and bonus products. In the case of non-durable goods, samples, bonus products, and coupons were identified as highly significant. Therefore, it is clear that sales promotion activities effectively foster a positive consumer attitude, motivating future purchases.

To support this perspective, Jallow and Dastane (2016) found that sales promotion schemes play a crucial role in influencing consumer purchasing decisions. Among the various schemes examined, several specific ones were identified as having a notable impact on consumers. These selected schemes include coupons, premiums, bonus packs, free samples, and price discounts, as they enhance value by offering additional benefits alongside the product purchase. The results of the empirical analysis indicated that all the sales promotion schemes were significant and effective in increasing purchase quantities.

Santini et al., (2015) says that they are both monetary and non-monetary forms of sales promotion, while also exploring the direct relationship between perceived value and the attractiveness of promotions. The findings revealed a significant moderating relationship between sales promotions and the variables under consideration. They believe retail managers can enhance their promotional strategies by taking into account the various forms of sales promotions that appeal to customers.

2.4 Gap in Literature

Numerous studies have extensively explored the impact of sales promotions on business performance; however, there remains a low research specifically focused on certain sales promotion tools, such as rebates, quantity price discounts, exhibitions, and financing options available to distributors or suppliers. Most existing studies tend to concentrate on broad promotional strategies, thereby neglecting the effects of these specific tools on business

performance. Additionally, the perspectives of intermediaries, like wholesalers and retailers, regarding the effectiveness of these tools in driving purchases and sales have not been adequately examined. This gap highlights the need to examine how these untapped tools influence purchasing behavior and sales metrics, particularly from the viewpoint of individuals within the distribution network. By focusing on this area, the research aims to offer a more detailed understanding of how targeted sales promotions influence business performance.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.0 Preamble

The chapter outlines the methodology, detailing the approaches utilized in the research work. It comprehensively addresses the objectives and procedures involved in conducting the study. This section will clarify the research process utilized for the research design, the study population, the determination of sample size, sampling methods, sample frame, the procedure for gathering data, and the research instruments used. Furthermore, it will address the validity and reliability of the research findings, as well as the ethical considerations that were taken into account.

3.1 Research Design

This study will adopt survey methodology to explore the correlation between sales promotion and business performance. This design is particularly advantageous as it allows for the generalization of findings to a wider population. The survey approach will assist in validating the proposed hypotheses, which are associated with positive outcomes.

3.2 Population of the Study

The term "population" refers to the entire group of cases from which a sample is selected. In this instance, the study population is limited to the employees of KAM-WIRE Manufacturing situated in Ilorin. The population will focus on employees from various departments of the organization, which encompass the sales and distribution department, accounting and finance department, marketing and product development, corporate risk and project management department, regulatory and external relations department, and operatives supporting various operational needs. Based on data available on the company's LinkedIn page, KAM-WIRE Manufacturing has an estimated workforce of 300 employees [Source <https://www.linkedin.com/company/kam-wiremanufacturing/>].

3.3 Sample Size Determination

The study adopts a simple random sampling technique to gather required data from Kam-Wire Manufacturing located in Ilorin. The study will use a sample size calculated using the Taro Yamane formula, which is commonly used in social science research. The size of the sample has a significant impact on the generalizability of the findings. The Taro Yamane formula was applied under the assumption of a 95% confidence level, which implies 5% tolerance error. The formula is presented below.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where;

n = sample size

N = population size

e = tolerance error

1 = constant

Therefore;

$$n = ?$$

$$N = 300$$

$$e = 5\%$$

$$n = \frac{300}{1 + 300(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{300}{1 + 300(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{300}{1 + 0.75}$$

$$n = \frac{300}{1.75}$$

$$n = 171.43 \sim 171$$

$n = 171$ respondents.

3.4 Sampling Frame

The sampling frame of this study will encompass all employees within the Kam-wire Manufacturing Company, thereby aligning with the study's objectives and facilitating a more manageable sample selection process.

3.5 Sampling Technique and Procedure

Sampling techniques refers to the procedure of choosing a subset from the entire population. For this study, a probability sampling method will be adopted, specifically utilizing simple random sampling techniques. This approach ensures that every element within the population has a known likelihood of being selected as part of the sample. The use of random sampling techniques enhances the generalizability of the results.

3.6 Data Collection Procedure

The main source of data collection for this study will be a primary source. The primary source will consist of administering a questionnaire. Data will be gathered through online surveys, which will be conducted using platforms such as Google Forms. To ensure a high

response rate, respondents will be encouraged to complete and submit the questionnaire immediately.

3.7 Research Instruments

The study will employ a structured questionnaire to gather responses from the selected respondents, specifically the staff of Kam-Wire. This questionnaire will feature a series of questions printed on a form or a collection of forms distributed to the respondents. It will utilize a closed-ended format with a five-point Likert scale, which will include options for agree (A), strongly agree (SA), undecided (UD), disagree (D), and strongly disagree (SD). The researcher will ensure that the language used in the questions is clear and comprehensible, facilitating accurate responses from the respondents.

3.8 Validity of Research Instrument

Validity testing connotes the degree to which the test actually measures what it is intended to measure. To ensure the validity of the research instrument, content validity will be established through a thorough review by the researcher's supervisor. The questionnaire will be carefully examined to assess the appropriateness of language, relevance to the subject matter, alignment with the study's objectives, and comprehensive coverage of key content areas.

3.9 Reliability of Research Instrument

Reliability denotes a measurement that provides uniform outcomes with consistent values. For the purposes of this research, all items included in the questionnaire will be guaranteed by maintaining consistent administration and conducting an analysis of internal consistency. This approach will strengthen the dependability of the data gathered. To evaluate reliability, a pilot test will be performed with a small group of employees from a comparable organization. This pilot test will assist in identifying any potential problems with the questionnaire,

including unclear or ambiguous questions, thereby ensuring that the final version of the instrument yields consistent results when applied to a larger sample.

3.10 Method of Data Analysis

Both qualitative and quantitative data will undergo analysis through statistical methods, including regression analysis, while document analysis will be employed to examine the relationships and impacts of independent variables on dependent variables as outlined in the study's hypothesis. Additionally, data collected from fieldwork will be analyzed using frequency distribution as a descriptive statistical method. This approach will be employed to present the percentage of demographic information and to illustrate the levels of agreement and disagreement regarding the research statement in the closed-ended questionnaire.

3.11 Ethical Consideration

The study presents no immediate risk to the respondents and complies with the established ethical standards in the field of management sciences. Respondents will not be pressured to complete the questionnaire; instead, they will receive a comprehensive explanation of the research aims. The confidentiality of respondents will be strictly maintained throughout the duration of this study. Additionally, this research will respect all ethical principles concerning the confidential information about the respondents, which will be used responsibly and shared only with the explicit consent and approval of the pertinent organization. The data gathered will be analyzed objectively, ensuring that there is no bias or distortion of the information.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.0 Preamble

This chapter focuses on data presentation, analysis and interpretation, and hypothesis testing. The various questions in the questionnaire are analyzed using simple percentage and the hypotheses are tested using the ordinary least square regression with the use SPSS 20 application.

4.1 Presentation of Data

The responses from the questionnaires were very encouraging, that is to say out of One hundred and Seventy-One (171) copies of questionnaires administered and distributed to the population, One hundred and forty eight (148) was correctly filled and returned to the researcher, this is recorded as 86.5% success rate while 30 of the questionnaires were not returned to the researcher, which is recorded as 13.5%. The questionnaires collected were deductively analyzed and represented in tables, percentage, and linear regression and co-efficient used for hypothesis testing.

Table 4.1: Presentation of Data

Questionnaire	Frequency	Percentage
Returned	148	86.5%
Not Returned/ InCorrectly Filled	23	13.5%
Total	171	100%

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2025

4.2 Data Analysis and Interpretation

The questionnaire was divided into two parts;

Part A: This contained respondents' Demographic data

Part B: This serve the focus of respondents' assessment for evaluation

4.2.1 Analysis of Demographic Data

For clarity and avoidance of possible ambiguities, tables are used to present the results drawn from each of the questions administered.

Table 4.2.2 Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	110	74.1	74.1	74.1
Female	38	25.9	25.9	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2025

The survey data reveals a significant gender imbalance among the respondents. A large majority, 74.1%, are male, while only 25.9% are female. This indicates that males constitute almost three-quarters of the sample, reflecting a predominantly male participant group in this survey. The data, sourced from the Author's Field Survey (2025), highlights the need to consider gender perspectives in further analyses, especially when understanding trends or making decisions based on this sample.

Table 4.2.3 AGE Group

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18-25	9	4.4	4.4	4.4
26- 35	116	54.6	54.6	59.0
36-45	86	40.4	40.4	99.5
46- above	2	.5	.5	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2025

The survey data collected in 2025 shows that the majority of respondents fall within the 26-35 age range, making up 54.6% of the total sample. A significant portion, 40.4%, is in the 36-45 group, suggesting a mature, yet active segment. The younger age group of 18-25 represents only 4.4% of the respondents, while those aged 46 and above account for a very small proportion at 0.5%. This distribution indicates a predominantly mid-aged workforce with relatively few respondents from the youngest and oldest age brackets.

Table 4.2.4 Educational Qualification

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	NCE/OND	52	29.0	29.0	29.0
	HND/B.SC	93	57.4	57.4	57.4
	MBA/M.Sc.	3	13.7	13.7	100.0
	Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The data from the Author’s Field Survey, 2025, reveals that among the 148 respondents, the majority (57.4%) hold HND or B.Sc. qualifications, indicating a strong foundation in undergraduate education. Nearly one-third (29.0%) possess NCE/OND credentials, suggesting a significant portion has achieved certificate or diploma-level education. A smaller segment (13.7%) has pursued advanced studies, earning an MBA or M.Sc. degree. This distribution highlights that while most individuals have completed foundational tertiary education, a modest group has further advanced their academic qualifications.

Table 4.2.5 Managerial Position

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Senior Level	4	29.5	29.5	29.5
	Middle Level	119	68.9	68.9	98.4
	Foreman	25	1.6	1.6	100.0
	Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The data categorizes managerial positions into Senior Level, Middle Level, and Foreman roles among 148 respondents. Middle Level management is the largest group, representing 68.9% (119 individuals). Senior Level positions make up 29.5% of the sample, while Foreman roles account for 1.6%. This distribution indicates a dominant presence of middle-level managers within the organization. The cumulative percentages confirm that all managerial roles are accounted for. Overall, the findings suggest an organizational structure with a strong emphasis on middle management.

Table 4.2.6 Department

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Sales & Distribution	93	57.4	57.4	57.4
	Acc & Fin	52	29.0	29.0	29.0
	Mkt & Prod.	3	13.7	13.7	100.0
	Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table reveals that most respondents belong to the Sales & Distribution department, accounting for 57.4% of the sample. The Accounting & Finance department follows with 29.0% of respondents. The Marketing & Production department is represented by 13.7% of the sample. Notably, the frequency counts indicate 93 for Sales & Distribution, 52 for Accounting & Finance, and 3 for Marketing & Production, suggesting a predominantly Sales & Distribution-focused group, while the Marketing & Production category appears underrepresented.

Table 4.2.7 Work Experience

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 0–2 years	9	4.4	4.4	4.4
3-5 years	116	54.6	54.6	59.0
6-10 years	86	40.4	40.4	99.5
10 years and above	2	.5	.5	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The survey data shows that most participants have mid-level experience. Specifically, 54.6% have 3–5 years and 40.4% have 6–10 years of experience. Only a small fraction (4.4%) are early in their careers with 0–2 years, and just 0.5% have over 10 years of experience. This suggests a predominantly young to mid-career workforce.

Table 4.2.8 Kam Wire Manufacturing frequently offers promotional discounts to attract customers.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	52	35.1	35.1	35.1
Agree	79	52.9	52.9	87.9
Valid Undecided	4	2.9	2.9	90.8
Disagree	16	9.2	9.2	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table above illustrate the question which state that Kam wire manufacturing frequently offers promotional discounts to attract customers., depicts that strongly agree consist of 52 (35.1%) respondents, agree consist of 79 (52.9%) respondents undecided consist of 4 (2.9%) respondents and Disagree consist of 16 (9.2%) respondents this table indicates that agree has the highest respondents of 79 (52.9%) and Undecided has the lowest respondents of 4 (2.9).

Table 4.2.9 Promotions like Buy-One-Get-One-Free influence customer purchase decisions.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	34	23.0	23.0	23.0
Agree	93	62.6	62.6	85.6
Undecided	21	14.4	14.4	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table above which question state that promotions like buy-one-get-one-free influence customer purchase decisions. indicates that 34 respondents with 23.0% are for strongly agreed, 93 respondents with 62.6% are for Agreed and 21 respondents with 14.4% are for Undecided, this statement indicates that agreed has the highest respondents of 93 (62.2%) and undecided has the lowest respondents of 21 (14.4%).

Table 4.2.10 Customers tend to buy more when temporary price discounts are offered.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	2	1.1	1.1	1.1
Agree	121	82.2	82.2	83.3
Undecided	3	2.3	2.3	85.6
Disagree	21	14.4	14.4	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table above illustrate the question that customers tend to buy more when temporary price discounts are offered, indicates that strongly agree consist of 2 (1.1%) respondents, agree consist of 121 (82.2%) respondents undecided consist of 3 (2.3%) respondents and Disagree consist of 21 (14.4%) respondents this table indicates that agree has the highest respondents of 121 (82.2%) and Strongly agreed has the lowest respondents of 2 (1.1%).

Table 4.2.11 Customers are more likely to choose Kam Wire over competitors when sales promotions are active

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	69	46.6	46.6	46.6
Valid Agree	37	25.3	25.3	71.8
Valid Undecided	42	28.2	28.2	100.0
Valid Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table above which question state that customers are more likely to choose Kam wire over competitors when sales promotions are active indicates that 69 respondents with 46.6% are for strongly agreed, 37 respondents with 25.3% are for Agreed and 42 respondents with 28.2% are for Undecided, this statement indicates that strongly agreed has the highest respondents of 69 (46.6%) and agreed has the lowest respondents of 37 (25.3%).

Table 4.2.12 Customers are influenced by promotional messages when shopping.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	42	28.4	28.4	28.4
Valid Agree	83	56.1	56.1	84.5
Valid Undecided	23	15.5	15.5	100.0
Valid Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table above which question state that customers are influenced by promotional messages when shopping indicates that 42 respondents with 28.4% are for strongly agreed, 83 respondents with 56.1% are for Agreed and 23 respondents with 15.1% are for Undecided, this statement indicates that agreed has the highest respondents of 83 (56.1%) and undecided has the lowest respondents of 23 (15.5%).

Table 4.2.13 Promotional campaigns have improved customer awareness of Kam Wire Manufacturing products.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	105	70.7	70.7	70.7
Agree	22	14.9	14.9	85.6
Valid Undecided	8	5.2	5.2	90.8
Disagree	14	9.2	9.2	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table above illustrate the question which state that promotional campaigns have improved customer awareness of Kam wire manufacturing products. depicts that strongly agree consist of 105 (70.7%) respondents, agree consist of 22 (14.9%) respondents undecided consist of 8 (5.2%) respondents and Disagree consist of 14 (9.2%) respondents this table indicates that Strongly agree has the highest respondents of 105 (70.7%) and Undecided has the lowest respondents of 8 (5.2%).

Table 4.2.14 The company’s loyalty programs and reward offers help in retaining customers.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	44	29.3	29.3	29.3
Valid Agree	90	60.9	60.9	90.2
Undecided	15	9.8	9.8	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table above which question state the company’s loyalty programs and reward offers help in retaining customers indicates that 44 respondents with 29.3% are for strongly agreed, 90 respondents with 60.9% are for Agreed and 15 respondents with 9.8% are for Undecided, this

statement indicates that agreed has the highest respondents of 90 (60.2%) and undecided has the lowest respondents of 15 (9.8%).

Table 4.2.15 Sponsoring trade fairs and exhibitions enhances Kam Wire Manufacturing’s brand visibility.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	80	54.0	54.0	54.0
Agree	34	23.0	23.0	77.0
Valid Undecided	20	13.8	13.8	90.8
Disagree	14	9.2	9.2	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table above which question state that sponsoring trade fairs and exhibitions enhances kam wire manufacturing’s brand visibility shows that 80 respondents with 54.0% are for strongly agreed, 34 respondents with 23.0% are for Agreed and 20 respondents with 13.8% are for Undecided, 14 respondents with 9.2% are for Disagree, this statement indicates that strongly agreed has the highest respondents of 80 (54.0%) and Disagree has the lowest respondents of 14 (9.2%).

Table 4.2.16 The sales team receives positive feedback from customers regarding the company’s promotional strategies.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	26	17.8	17.8	17.8
Valid Agree	103	69.5	69.5	87.4
Undecided	19	12.6	12.6	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table above illustrate the The sales team receives positive feedback from customers regarding the company’s promotional strategies depicts that strongly agree consist of 26 (17.8%) respondents, agree consist of 103 (69.5%) respondents undecided consist of 6

(12.6%) respondents this statements indicates that Agree has the highest respondents of 103(69.5 %) and Undecided has the lowest respondents of 19 (12.6%).

Table 4.2.17 The more valuable a promotion is, the more likely customers are to recognize the brand.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	13	8.8	8.8	8.8
Agree	111	75	75	83.8
Valid Undecided	3	2.3	2.3	86.1
Disagree	21	14	14	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table above illustrate the question that the more valuable a promotion is, the more likely customers are to recognize the brand, indicates that strongly agree consist of 13 (8.8%) respondents, agree consist of 111 (75%) respondents undecided consist of 3 (2.3%) respondents and Disagree consist of 21 (14%) respondents this table indicates that agree has the highest respondents of 111 (75%) and undecided has the lowest respondents of 3 (2.3%).

Table 4.2.18 Adjusting inventory based on the needs of the target audience reduces product wastage

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	30	20.1	20.1	20.1
Agree	86	58.0	58.0	78.2
Valid Undecided	34	11.5	11.5	89.7
Disagree	15	10.3	10.3	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table above which question state that adjusting inventory based on the needs of the target audience reduces product wastage shows that 30 respondents with 20.1% are for strongly agreed, 86 respondents with 58.0% are for Agreed, 34 respondents with 11.5% are for Undecided, and 15 respondents with 10.3% are for Disagree, this statement indicates that

Agreed has the highest respondents of 86 (58.0%) and Disagree has the lowest respondents of 15 (10.3%).

Table 4.2.19 Promotions for bulk purchases aimed at retailers enhance the rate of inventory turnover

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	28	19.0	19.0	19.0
Valid Agree	106	71.3	71.3	90.2
Valid Undecided	15	9.8	9.8	100.0
Valid Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2025

The table above which question state that promotions for bulk purchases aimed at retailers enhance the rate of inventory turnover indicates that 28 (19.0%) respondents are for strongly agreed, 106 (71.3%) respondents are for Agreed and 15 (9.8%) respondents are for Undecided, this statement indicates that agreed has the highest respondents of 106 (71.3%) and undecided has the lowest respondents of 15 (9.8%).

Table 4.2.20 Promotional offers aimed at wrong audience result in surplus stock

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	54	36.8	36.8	36.8
Valid Agree	79	53.4	53.4	90.2
Valid Undecided	1	.6	.6	90.8
Valid Disagree	14	9.2	9.2	100.0
Valid Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2025

The table above which question state that promotional offers aimed at wrong audience result in surplus stock Indicates that 54 (36.8%) respondents are for strongly agreed, 79 (53.4%) respondents are for Agreed 1 (.6%) respondents are for Undecided, and 14 (9.2%) are for Disagree this statement indicates that agreed has the highest respondents of 79 (53.4%) and undecided has the lowest respondent of 1 (.6%).

Table 4.2.21 Reaching the right wholesalers and retailers helps products sell faster and keeps inventory moving smoothly.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	110	74.1	74.1	74.1
Agree	24	16.1	16.1	90.2
Undecided	15	9.8	9.8	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table above which question state reaching the right wholesalers and retailers helps products sell faster and keeps inventory moving smoothly shows that 110 respondents with 74.1% are for strongly agreed, 24 respondents with 16.1% are for Agreed, 15 respondents with 9.8% are for Undecided this statement indicates that Strongly Agreed has the highest respondents of 110 (74.1%) and Undecided has the lowest respondents of 15 (9.8%).

Table 4.2.22 Failure to define a target audience limits industry growth and sales performance.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	105	70.7	70.7	70.7
Agree	22	14.9	14.9	85.6
Undecided	8	5.2	5.2	90.8
Disagree	14	9.2	9.2	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table above illustrate the question which state that Failure to define a target audience limits industry growth and sales performance depicts that strongly agree consist of 105 (70.7%) respondents, agree consist of 22 (14.9%) respondents undecided consist of 8 (5.2%) respondents and Disagree consist of 14 (9.2%) respondents this table indicates that Strongly

agree has the highest respondents of 105 (70.7%) and Undecided has the lowest respondents of 8 (5.2%).

Table 4.2.23 Seasonal promotions make work run more smoothly and help Kam Wire Manufacturing save money on extra costs

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	103	69.5	69.5	69.5
Agree	11	7.5	7.5	77.0
Valid Undecided	20	13.8	13.8	90.8
Disagree	14	9.2	9.2	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table above which question state that seasonal promotions make work run more smoothly and help Kam wire manufacturing save money on extra costs indicates that 103 respondents with 69.5% are for strongly agreed, 11 respondents with 7.5% are for Agreed, 20 respondents with 13.8% are for Undecided and 4 respondents with 9.2% are for Disagree this statement indicates that strongly agreed has the highest respondents of 103 (69.5%) and agreed has the lowest respondents of 11 (7.5%).

Table 4.2.24 Poor timing of sales promotions negatively affects business performance

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	26	17.8	17.8	17.8
Valid Agree	103	69.5	69.5	87.4
Undecided	19	12.6	12.6	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table above illustrate the question which state that poor timing of sales promotions negatively affects business performance, depicts that strongly agree consist of 26 (17.8%) respondents, agree consist of 103 (69.5%) respondents undecided consist of 19 (12.6%) respondents this statements indicates that Agree has the highest respondents of 103 (69.5 %) and Undecided has the lowest respondents of 19 (12.6%).

Table 4.2.25 Kam Wire Manufacturing effectively evaluates past seasonal promotions to improve future efficiency

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	69	46.6	46.6	46.6
Agree	37	25.3	25.3	71.8
Undecided	42	28.2	28.2	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table above which question state that Kam Wire Manufacturing effectively evaluates past seasonal promotions to improve future efficiency indicates that 69 respondents with 46.6% are for strongly agreed, 37 respondents with 25.3% are for Agreed and 42 respondents with 28.2% are for Undecided, this statement indicates that strongly agreed has the highest respondents of 42 (46.6%) and agreed has the lowest respondents of 37 (25.3%).

Table 4.2.26 Delays in the preparation for seasonal sales promotions negatively affect the performance of the company

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	54	36.8	36.8	36.8
Agree	79	53.4	53.4	90.2
Undecided	1	.6	.6	90.8
Disagree	14	9.2	9.2	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The table above which question state that delays in the preparation for seasonal sales promotions negatively affect the performance of the company Indicates that 54 (36.8%) respondents are for strongly agreed, 79 (53.4%) respondents are for Agreed 1(.6%) respondents are for Undecided, and 14 (9.2%) are for Disagree this statement indicates that

agreed has the highest respondents of 79 (53.4%) and undecided has the lowest respondent of 1 (.6%).

Table 4.2.27 Adapting to seasonal trends helps reduce waste and improve efficiency.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	44	29.7	29.7	29.7
Agree	80	54.1	54.1	83.8
Valid Undecided	3	2.3	2.3	86
Disagree	21	14	14	100.0
Total	148	100.0	100.0	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2025

The table above illustrate the question that Adapting to seasonal trends helps reduce waste and improve efficiency, indicates that strongly agree consist of 44 (29.7%) respondents, agree consist of 80 (54.1%) respondents undecided consist of 3 (2.3%) respondents and Disagree consist of 21 (14%) respondents this table indicates that agree has the highest respondents of 80 (54.1%) and undecided has the lowest respondents of 3 (2.3%).

4.3 Hypotheses Testing

4.3.1 Test for Hypothesis 1

H₀ There is no significant relationship between consumer promotion and consumer purchasing behavior in Kam-Wire manufacturing company.

H₁ There is a significant relationship between consumer promotion and consumer purchasing behavior in Kam-Wire manufacturing company.

Table 4.3.1.1 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.761 ^a	.579	.576	1.06033

a. Predictors: (Constant), Consumer promotion

The model summary as indicated in table 4.3.1.1 above shows that R Square is 0.579; this implies that 57% of variation in the dependent variable (Consumer purchasing behavior) were explained by the independent variable (Consumer promotion) while the remaining 43% is due to other variables that are not included in the model. This mean that the regression (model formulated) is useful for making predictions since the value of R² is close to 1

Table 4.3.1.2 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	107.260	1	107.260	30.725	.000 ^b
	Residual	439.857	146	3.491		
	Total	547.117	147			

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer purchasing behavior

b. Predictors: (Constant), Consumer promotion

The table above summarized the results of an analysis of variation in the dependent variable with large value of regression sum of squares (107.260) in comparison to the residual sum of squares with value of 439.857 (this value indicated that the model does not fail to explain a lot of the variation in the dependent variables. However, the estimated F-value (30.725) as given in the table above with significance value of 0.000, which is less than p-value of 0.05 (p<0.05) which means that the independent variable as a whole can jointly influence the increment in the dependent variable (Consumer purchasing behavior).

Table 4.3.1.3 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.354	.732		5.951	.000

Consumer promotion	.472	.085	.443	5.543	.000
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a. Dependent Variable: Consumer purchasing behavior

Interpretation

The dependent variable as shown in the table 4.3.1.3 was Consumer purchasing behavior. This was used as a yardstick to examine the impact between the two variables (i.e., Consumer promotion and Consumer purchasing behavior). The predictors is Consumer promotion, as depicted in table 4.3.1.3, it is obvious that there is a direct relationship between Consumer promotion and Consumer purchasing behavior.

According to the result in the table above Consumer promotion t-test coefficient is 5.543 and the P-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 (i.e., $P < 0.05$). This means that these variables are statistically significant at 5% significant level.

Decision Rule

As a result of the outcome, the Null Hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected on the basis that the p-value is less 0.05. Hence the alternative hypothesis is accepted, that Consumer promotion has a significant effect on consumer purchasing behavior on achieving higher consumer purchasing behavior of Kam Wire manufacturing company. Hence, it explains how significant hypothesis one is to be recommended to Consumer purchasing behavior.

4.3.2 Test for Hypothesis 2

H_0 : There is no significant impact of promotional value on brand recognition in Kam-Wire manufacturing company

H₁: There is a significant impact of promotional value on brand recognition in Kam-Wire manufacturing company

Table 4.3.2.1 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.517 ^a	.667	.662	1.63511

a. Predictors: (Constant), Promotional value

The model summary as indicated in table 4.3.2.1 above shows that R Square is 0.667; this implies that 66% of variation in the dependent variable (Brand recognition) were explained by the independent variable (Promotional value) while the remaining 34% is due to other variables that are not included in the model. This mean that the regression (model formulated) is useful for making predictions since the value of R² is close to 1

Table 4.3.2.2 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	155.475	1	155.475	59.007	.000 ^b
	Residual	331.994	146	2.635		
	Total	487.469	147			

a. Dependent Variable: Brand recognition

b. Predictors: (Constant), Promotional value

The table above summarized the results of an analysis of variation in the dependent variable with large value of regression sum of squares (155.475) in comparison to the residual sum of squares with value of 331.994 (this value indicated that the model does not fail to explain a lot of the variation in the dependent variables. However, the estimated F-value (59.007) as given in the table above with significance value of 0.000, which is less than p-value of 0.05

($p < 0.05$) which means that the independent variable as a whole can jointly influence the increment in the dependent variable (Brand recognition).

Table 4.3.2.3 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.603	.636		5.668	.000
	Promotional value	.568	.074	.565	7.682	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Brand recognition

Interpretation

The dependent variable Brand recognition was used as a yardstick to examine the impact between the two variables (i.e. Promotional value and Brand recognition). The predictors is Promotional value, as depicted in table 4.3.2.3 it is obvious that there is a direct relationship between Promotional value and Brand recognition.

According to the result in the table above Promotional value t-test coefficient is 7.682 and the P-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 (i.e. $P < 0.05$). This means that these variables are statistically significant at 5% significant level.

Decision Rule

As a result of the outcome, the Null Hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected on the basis that the p-value is less 0.05. Hence the alternative hypothesis is accepted, that Promotional value has significant effect on Brand recognition. Hence, it explains how significant hypothesis one is to be recommended to brand recognition.

4.3.3 Test for Hypothesis 3

H_0 : Target audience has no effect on inventory turnover in Kam-Wire manufacturing company

H_1 : Target audience has an effect on inventory turnover in Kam-Wire manufacturing company

Table 4.3.3.1 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.588 ^a	.922	.342	1.04629

a. Predictors: (Constant), Target audience

The model summary as indicated in table 4.3.3.1 above shows that R Square is 0.92; this implies that 92% of variation in the dependent variable (Inventory turnover) were explained by the independent variable (Target audience) while the remaining 8% is due to other variables that are not included in the model. This mean that the regression (model formulated) is useful for making predictions since the value of R^2 is close to 1

Table 4.3.3.2 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	119.286	1	119.286	35.131	.000 ^b
	Residual	427.832	146	3.395		
	Total	547.117	147			

a. Dependent Variable: Inventory turnover

b. Predictors: (Constant), Target audience

The table above summarized the results of an analysis of variation in the dependent variable with large value of regression sum of squares (119.286) in comparison to the residual sum of squares with value of 427.832 (this value indicated that the model does not fail to explain a lot of the variation in the dependent variables. However, the estimated F-value (35.131) as given in the table above with significance value of 0.000, which is less than p-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) which means that the independent variable as a whole can jointly influence the increment in the dependent variable (Inventory turnover).

Table 4.3.3.3 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.191	.878		3.635	.000
	Target audience	.611	.103	.467	5.927	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Inventory turnover

Interpretation

The dependent variable Inventory turnover was used as a yardstick to examine the impact between the two variables (i.e. Target audience and Inventory turnover). The predictors is Target audience this has a direct relationship between Target audience and Inventory turnover.

According to the result in the table above t-test coefficient is 5.927 and the P-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 (i.e. $P < 0.05$). This means that these variables are statistically significant at 5% significant level.

4.3.4 Test for Hypothesis 4

H_0 There is no significant difference between seasonal timing and operational efficiency in Kam-Wire manufacturing company.

H_1 There is a significant difference between seasonal timing and operational efficiency in Kam-Wire manufacturing company.

Table 4.3.4.1 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.788 ^a	.620	.618	1.04369

a. Predictors: (Constant), Seasonal timing

The model summary as indicated in table 4.3.4.1 above shows that R Square is 0.62; this implies that 62% of variation in the dependent variable (Operational efficiency) were explained by the independent variable (Seasonal timing) while the remaining 8% is due to other variables that are not included in the model. This mean that the regression (model formulated) is useful for making predictions since the value of R^2 is close to 1

Table 4.3.4.2 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	176.641	1	176.641	71.605	.000 ^b
	Residual	310.828	146	2.467		
	Total	487.469	147			

a. Dependent Variable: Operational efficiency

b. Predictors: (Constant), Seasonal timing

The table above summarized the results of an analysis of variation in the dependent variable with large value of regression sum of squares (176.641) in comparison to the residual sum of squares with value of 310.828 (this value indicated that the model does not fail to explain a

lot of the variation in the dependent variables. However, the estimated F-value (71.605) as given in the table above with significance value of 0.000, which is less than p-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) which means that the independent variable as a whole can jointly influence the increment in the dependent variable (Operational efficiency).

Table 4.3.4.3 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.137	.748		2.856	.005
	Seasonal timing	.743	.088	.602	8.462	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Operational efficiency

Interpretation

The dependent variable operational efficiency was used as a yardstick to examine the impact between the two variables (i.e. Seasonal timing and Operational efficiency). The predictors is Seasonal timing, it is obvious that there is a direct relationship between Seasonal timing and Operational efficiency.

According to the result in the table above Seasonal timing t-test coefficient is 8.462 and the P-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 (i.e. $P < 0.05$). This means that these variables are statistically significant at 5% significant level.

Decision Rule

As a result of the outcome, the Null Hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected on the basis that the p-value is less 0.05. Hence the alternative hypothesis is accepted, that Seasonal timing has significant

effect on Operational efficiency. Hence, it explains how significant hypothesis two is to be recommended to operational efficiency.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

This study examines ‘impact of sales promotion on business performance’. The X construct is sales promotion in which two variables were to demystify the concept of impact of sales promotion on business performance which includes four variables which are consumer promotion, promotional value, target audience and seasonal timing while Y construct which is business performance consists of four variables which are consumer purchasing behavior, brand recognition, inventory turnover and operational efficiency. The study tries to examine whether sales promotion affects the performance of Kam Wire manufacturing Industries. The findings however show a linear relationship between variables used to measure the two constructs after the postulation of four hypotheses which invariably declares that promotion plays an important role in contributing to performance of Kam Wire Industries. Also, from information gathered through questionnaires distributed within the staffs of this organization. It was detected that sales promotion plays a pivotal role in the performance of Kam Wire Manufacturing Industry.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.0 Preamble

This chapter is the final part of this study and it is divided into summary of findings, conclusions made in the course of this study, recommendations made to the case study, sector, regulating body and other interested bodies. In addition, this chapter addresses the areas in which further studies can be conducted.

5.1 Summary

This section summarizes the findings of the study in line with the stated hypotheses. The major outcomes are presented below:

Hypothesis one states that there is no significant impact of consumer promotion on the consumer purchasing behavior of Kam Wire Manufacturing. The null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This indicates that consumer promotion significantly influences consumer purchasing behavior at Kam Wire Manufacturing. The study further revealed that over the years, consumer promotion has played a crucial role in shaping purchasing decisions, leading to continuous improvement in customer engagement and overall performance. This finding aligns with the work of Jo Davies and Martin Graff (2017), who also confirmed that consumer promotion has a significant impact on business performance.

Hypothesis two states that promotional value has no effect on the brand recognition of Kam Wire Manufacturing in Ilorin. The null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternative

hypothesis was accepted. The study found that promotional value plays a vital role in enhancing brand recognition. It was revealed that placing serious emphasis on promotional value contributes greatly to the visibility and awareness of Kam Wire Manufacturing in Ilorin, Kwara State.

Hypothesis three states that the target audience does not have any effect on the inventory turnover of Kam Wire Manufacturing. The null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis was accepted. The findings showed that the target audience significantly affects inventory turnover at Kam Wire Manufacturing. The study revealed that inventory turnover improves when the right audience is identified and targeted effectively. This result is in agreement with the study by Mavis (2016), who established that defining and reaching the appropriate target audience is one of the most effective strategies for enhancing inventory turnover.

Hypothesis four states that there is no significant impact of seasonal timing on the operational efficiency of Kam Wire Manufacturing in Ilorin. The null hypothesis was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis was accepted, indicating that seasonal timing has a significant impact on operational efficiency. The study revealed that increases in operational efficiency are often influenced by proper alignment with seasonal demand and timing. This finding supports the conclusion of Ukpafe (2015), who noted that seasonal timing plays a crucial role in improving operational efficiency in manufacturing businesses.

5.2 Conclusions

The study concludes that consumer promotions significantly influence purchasing behavior at Kam-Wire Manufacturing Company. Promotional incentives such as discounts, bonuses, and loyalty rewards positively shape consumer buying decisions, leading to increased purchase volumes and stronger brand loyalty. The findings also reveal that promotional activities contribute meaningfully to brand recognition, as well-executed campaigns enhance the visibility and recall of the Kam-Wire brand, positioning it favorably in the minds of both existing and potential customers. Furthermore, the study demonstrates that having a clearly defined and well-understood target audience plays a vital role in optimizing inventory turnover. When products and marketing strategies are aligned with the needs of the intended audience, Kam-Wire can effectively minimize excess stock, reduce holding costs, and improve sales cycles. Additionally, the research shows that aligning operational activities with seasonal demand patterns improves overall efficiency. Proper anticipation and planning for peak and off-peak periods allow for better resource utilization, reduced waste, and timely product availability, which together support smoother and more effective operations.

5.3 Recommendations

In relations to the above findings and conclusion, the study recommends that;

- i. It is recommended that Kam-Wire Manufacturing Company intensify its consumer promotion strategies by adopting more engaging and reward-based promotional campaigns. This could include discounts, free samples, loyalty rewards, and digital engagement activities. By tailoring promotions to meet the preferences of its target consumers, the company can stimulate repeat purchases, influence buyer decisions, and build stronger customer loyalty.

- ii. Kam-Wire Manufacturing Company should invest in consistent and high-value promotional activities that emphasize its brand identity and core values. These could include sponsorships, community engagement, media campaigns, and strategic use of digital platforms to amplify brand visibility. Leveraging brand storytelling and clear brand messaging in promotional materials will enhance recognition and trust.
- iii. It is recommended that Kam-Wire Manufacturing Company conduct a thorough market segmentation analysis to better understand its target audience and align its inventory management strategies accordingly. By tailoring product availability to the needs and purchasing behaviors of specific customer segments, the company can improve inventory turnover, reduce holding costs, and prevent stock outs or overstocking.
- iv. Kam-Wire Manufacturing Company should align its production and supply chain operations with seasonal demand patterns. Planning and scheduling operations based on accurate seasonal sales data will help the company optimize resource utilization, reduce downtime, and manage operational costs.

5.4 Policy Implications of the Study

The results of this study offer the following policy implications:

- i. **Promotion Strategy Policy:** It is imperative that organizations establish structured promotional policies that align with consumer behavior trends. This includes setting clear guidelines on the timing, type, and frequency of sales promotions to avoid market fatigue or loss of perceived value.
- ii. **Target Audience Segmentation:** Businesses must adopt policy frameworks that emphasize the identification and targeting of specific customer segments. This ensures that promotional offers are effectively aligned with the preferences, needs, and purchasing

behaviors of the right audience, thereby minimizing inventory surplus and enhancing turnover.

iii. **Seasonal Sales Policy:** Organizations should institutionalize policies for managing seasonal demand fluctuations. Planning promotions in alignment with seasonal patterns can optimize operational efficiency, reduce costs, and improve customer satisfaction.

iv. **Regulatory Oversight:** Regulatory bodies such as the Consumer Protection Council (CPC) should develop and enforce standards to ensure transparency, fairness, and ethical considerations in the administration of sales promotions across industries.

v. **Brand Equity Considerations:** Firms should formulate long-term marketing policies that balance short-term promotional tactics with sustainable brand equity goals. Excessive or misaligned promotional activities can harm brand perception and profitability in the long run.

5.5 Delimitation of the Study

The study was limited geographically to Kam-Wire Manufacturing Company located in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria. This means that the research findings are context-specific and may not be directly applicable to other manufacturing firms operating in different regions or under varying economic conditions. The focus on a single location was primarily due to accessibility, time constraints, and the need to maintain a manageable scope for in-depth analysis.

Another limitation to this study is the narrowed focus on selected variables of sales promotion—namely consumer promotion, promotional value, target audience, and seasonal timing. Other marketing and organizational factors that could also influence business performance, such as advertising strategies, pricing policies, customer service quality, and distribution efficiency, were not considered within the scope of this research.

5.6 Suggestions for further studies

Future studies could compare the impact of sales promotions across industries and examine their short-term vs. long-term effects. Researchers may explore the effectiveness of digital vs. traditional promotional methods. Understanding consumer perception and cultural differences in response to promotions is also important. The role of promotions in brand equity and employee motivation can be explored. Lastly, studies could identify which types of promotions most effectively boost business performance.

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APPENDICES

LETTER OF INTRODUCTION

DEPARTMENT OF BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP

FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT AND SOCIAL SCIENCES

KWARA STATE UNIVERSITY, MALETE.

22nd April, 2025

Dear Sir/Madam,

**REQUEST TO COMPLETE RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE ON IMPACT OF
SALES PROMOTION ON BUSINESS PERFORMANCE
(A STUDY OF KAM WIRE MANUFACTURING COMPANY, KWARA STATE)**

I am a final year student of Kwara State University, currently conducting a research project on “The Impact of Sales Promotion on the Performance of Kam Wire Manufacturing Company, Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria.” This study is a requirement for the award of a Bachelor of Science (BSc) in Business Administration.

I kindly request your assistance in completing the attached questionnaire, which is strictly for academic purposes. Your responses will be treated with the utmost confidentiality and used solely for this research.

Thank you in advance for your time and cooperation.

Yours sincerely,

Olawale Abraham

21/27BA/01412

QUESTIONNAIRE

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

Instruction: Please answer the questions in each section by ticking the appropriate option (✓) or state your opinion as appropriate. Do not tick more than one option.

Gender: Male () Female ()

Age Group: 18-25 years () 26-35 years () 36-45 years () 46 years and above ()

Educational Qualification: Diploma/NCE () HND/Bachelor's Degree () Master's Degree/MBA ()

Managerial Position: Senior level () Middle level () Foreman ()

Department: Sales and Distribution () Accounting and Finance () Marketing and Product Development () Operations () Others (Please specify) _____

Work Experience: 0–2 years () 3-5 years () 6-10 years () 10 years and above()

SECTION B

Investigating the Impact of sales promotion on business performance

Kindly indicate the extent of your agreement or disagreement with the statements by ticking the appropriate boxes below:

Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (UD), Disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD).

S/N	Statements	SA	A	UD	D	SD
	To what does consumer promotion affect consumer purchase					
1	Kam Wire Manufacturing frequently offers promotional discounts to attract customers.					
2	Promotions like Buy-One-Get-One-Free influence customer purchase decisions.					
3	Customers tend to buy more when temporary price discounts are offered.					

4	Customers are more likely to choose Kam Wire over competitors when sales promotions are active.					
5	Customers are influenced by promotional messages when shopping.					
	To what extent does promotional value have a significant impact on brand recognition					
6	Promotional campaigns have improved customer awareness of Kam Wire Manufacturing products.					
7	The company's loyalty programs and reward offers help in retaining customers.					
8	Sponsoring trade fairs and exhibitions enhances Kam Wire Manufacturing's brand visibility.					
9	The sales team receives positive feedback from customers regarding the company's promotional strategies.					
10	The more valuable a promotion is, the more likely customers are to recognize the brand.					
	To what extent does target audience have a significant effect on industry turnover					
11	Adjusting inventory based on the needs of the target audience reduces product wastage.					
12	Promotions for bulk purchases aimed at retailers enhance the rate of inventory turnover.					
13	Promotional offers aimed at wrong audience result in surplus stock.					

14	Reaching the right wholesalers and retailers helps products sell faster and keeps inventory moving smoothly.					
15	Failure to define a target audience limits industry growth and sales performance.					
	How does seasonal timing impact operational efficiency					
16	Seasonal promotions make work run more smoothly and help Kam Wire Manufacturing save money on extra costs.					
17	Poor timing of sales promotions negatively affects business performance.					
18	Kam Wire Manufacturing effectively evaluates past seasonal promotions to improve future efficiency.					
19	Delays in the preparation for seasonal sales promotions negatively affect the performance of the company.					
20	Adapting to seasonal trends helps reduce waste and improve efficiency.					

Thank you for your participation.